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Anowar's Handbook International Trade and Marketing Management

Md. Anowar Hossain

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Page | 1

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Key note of handwritten book

This preprint book is helpful for industry experts, industry owners, marketing experts, students, researchers, professors and professionals in the field of *Trade and Marketing Management*. This handbook is written from author's notebook for exam preparation in Bachelor of Science in Textile Engineering.

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Tex-401

International trade and Marketing mgt.

Course instructor:

(Dr. Abu Zafar Mahmudul Haq)

Assistant Professor

Office hour: MW-9:30-12:00+1:30-3:00

International trade

*** write down the definition of International trade.

Ans:

International trade involves the exchange of goods and services across international boundaries.

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*** What are the causes of international trade?

Ans:

- (1) Due to labour shortage.
- (2) Due to capital shortage.
- (3) Due to shortage of natural resources.
- (4) Due to shortage of technology.

*** What are the benefits from international trade?

Ans:

- 1. One country will produce one product.
- 2. Both countries will produce both products.
- 3. Both countries will produce both products but on the basis of production efficiency.

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Summary: According to this way

international trade induces to create
specialisation.

*** why might countries not benefit from
specialisation through international trade?

Ans:

1. use of natural resources become narrow.
2. other resources, say human resources skill become narrow.

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*** Discuss the policies of conservation
conservatives?

Ans:

WS = World supply

DD = Domestic supply Demand

DS = Domestic supply

JM
↓
KL

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Direct method of trade conservative policies:

→ The way which induces to increase the price of imported goods, known as custom duty/ Tariff (সুদান)

→ Before any tariff, the price of imported goods P_0 , the domestic demand and domestic supply were M and OM

→ Therefore, imported volume was AM

→ After imposing tariff, price increases from P_0 to P_1

→ After price increasing

Domestic demand decreases M to L

Domestic supply A to K

Import volume AM to KL

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Indirect Method:

Quota:

A quota is a physical limitation which is imposed on a specific imported goods.

- impose → স্থাপ করা
- Quota → A proportional share.

Fig shown:

$P_0 \rightarrow$ ws is infinite

A country imports Q_0 to P_0
After imposing quota, $Q_1, P_0 \leq P_1$

Now domestic production will produce Q_1, Q_0

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Dumping:
It denotes a sale of goods abroad at prices lower than those prevailing in the local market.

The purpose behind it is to undercut the producers in the importing country.

Embargo:

It refers to an order issued by a government preventing the arrival or departure of a ship or restricting the import/export of specified goods.

Example:

The German ships were under embargo at the English port.

(Suspension of trade by authority)

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ff

*** what do you understand by "Brain Drain"
D = Procedure to a person who has left his/her country to work in another country.

Ans:

The immigration of highly educated workforces to another country.

*** what do you know about Reverse Brain Drain?

The return of highly educated workforces to their home countries.

*** what are the impacts of Brain Drain?

Ans:

Positive impacts:

1. Earnings ↑
2. Investment ↑
3. Economic + Social works ↑

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*** Q. What are the impacts of Reverse Brain Drain?

Ans:

1. Earnings ↓
2. Investment ↓
- 3.

The most important thing to note is that the brain drain is not just about the loss of skilled workers. It is also about the loss of knowledge and experience. When skilled workers leave, they take their knowledge and experience with them. This can be a major loss for the country. In addition, the loss of skilled workers can also lead to a loss of innovation and creativity. This is because skilled workers are often the ones who are most likely to come up with new ideas and solutions. Without them, the country may miss out on important innovations and discoveries. Finally, the loss of skilled workers can also lead to a loss of economic growth. Skilled workers are essential for many industries, and their loss can lead to a decline in productivity and output. This can have a significant impact on the country's economy.

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*** Discuss briefly about Export System?

Ans:

→ Shipping document

→ Names and addresses of the shipper

→ Port of exit and foreign port of unloading

→ Description of the goods and value

→ Export license number and

bill of lading

→ Carriers transporting the merchandise

→ Insurance certificate

[Bill of Lading

A contract of carriage

between shipper and carrier]

and many others which should be decided among the exporters and importers.

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Definition of Terms of Trade

Terms of Trade

Ans. [The ratio betw export and import is called terms of trade.]

Q. What's the Definition of Terms of Trade?

It acts as a ratio between the index of export prices and the index of import prices.

$$\text{Terms of Trade} = \frac{\text{index of export prices}}{\text{index of import prices}} \times 100$$

Q. How does the increase the terms of trade?

The terms of trade index will fall if import prices rises relative to export prices.

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→ If export prices rise relative to import prices, the terms of trade be effective (rise)

Q. What is meant by movement in the terms of trade?

→ A rise in the terms of trade is described as a favourable movement/improvement in the T.D.

→ A fall in the T.D is described as unfavourable

Q. What are the causes of movements in the terms of trade?

Ans:

1. A decrease in foreign demand for the country's exports and thus the price of exports.

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Marketing management

Marketing management is defined as the analysis, planning, implementation and control of programs designed to bring about desired exchanges with target markets for the purpose of achieving organizational activities.

Analysis

Input market

Output market

Determinants

- ① Skilled
- ② Unskilled

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Wage	Demand	Supply	Stk. of MKT	Pressure on Wage
W_1	DL_1	SL_1	$S > D$	Downward
W_E	DE	SE	$D = S$	Market Neutral
W_0	DL_0	SL_0	$D > S$	Upward

$W_0 \rightarrow DL_0 > SL_0$

$W_1 \rightarrow DL_1 < SL_1$

$W_E \rightarrow DL = SL$

Questions: Determination of Labour

Market equilibrium

strategy

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At wage - w_0 (Table and fig)

$DL > SL$

Because $w \downarrow$ $DL \uparrow$ and $w \downarrow$ $SL \downarrow$

Due this imbalance between DL and SL ,
it expects higher price otherwise SL
will not increase.

Supp

At wage - w_1

$DL < SL$

Because $w \uparrow$ $DL \downarrow$ and $w \uparrow$ $SL \uparrow$

Still it sees an imbalance between DL and SL

Finally,

w_E is the wage where $DL = SL$
This indicates equilibrium of
wage and number of workers

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Retardation of labor market
Textile product industry:

- ↳ Heavy plant
- ↳ Expensive
- ↳ Barriers of entry

Ques: How a textile industry can reach equilibrium price?

Price

Q₂ Q_E Q₁ Q

P₂ P_E P_D

O

kinky shaped demand curve

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In fig: $OP = \text{Price}$, $OQ = \text{Qty}$, $D = \text{Demand}$

At prices P_2 , $Q_E > Q_2$

where Demand is very elastic, the Demand curve is kinked at E. If prices are raised, the competitors will not follow suit and a large part of his market will be lost.

At prices P_1 , $Q_E < Q_1$

where Demand is inelastic. Because the oligopolist believes if he cuts his price, his rivals will follow suit and he will gain relatively little in the way of additional sales.

So, At prices P_E

the textile industry can reach equilibrium price.

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Ques: How a textile industry reach equilibrium price?

In figure

S represents the supply of land available in the economy as a whole

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and D_2 shows the demand of
producers for the use of land.

Because the supply of land is
perfectly inelastic, an increase
in demand from $D_2 \rightarrow D_1$ will
change land rent from $R_2 \rightarrow R_1$

Ques Explain the price determination
of land to establish a textile
industry
or,

How can you search land for
your expected industry.

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Skilled Labour:

Demand + supply → inelastic

where $Q_0, Q_1 < P_0, P_1$

When supply responds a little in response with the change of price, indicates inelasticity of supply

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When supply responds greater in response with the changes of price indicates the price elasticity of supply.

In such case, $E_{sp} > 1$

Q. What do you mean by product strategy?

Ans:

It is concerned with the decisions on the range of products a firm must offer to achieve target profit, growth and market shares consistent with total demand and business conditions.

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b. Flexibility : (নমনীয়তা)

With changing demand of customers, firm should make flexibility.

Q. Discuss about Market research?

Ans:

The device of employing the scientific method in the solution of marketing problems.

Scope of market research:

1. The size of the market
2. Products
3. channels and methods of distribution
4. Marketing policies
5. Selling activities
6. Publicity

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3. To obtain the good will of consumers.

*** Discuss about the channel of distribution?

Ans: The movement of goods and services between the point of production and the point of consumption through organizations.

*** How you can select a channel of distribution?

Ans:

1. Nature of market
2. Nature of product
3. Degree of competition
4. Size of organization.

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